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Abdulla Qahhor “Bemor” va “O’g’ri” hikoyalarini yosh avlodga o’rgatishda qo’llaniluvchi innovatsion metodik tavsiyalar

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada o’zbek adibi Abdulla Qahhor “Bemor” va “O’g’ri” hikoyalarini yosh avlodga o’rgatishda qo’llaniluvchi innovatsion metodik tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan. Asosan quyidagi zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanilgan: “Atamalar izohi”, “Muammoli vaziyat”, “KZIX”, “Besh bo’lakli matn”, “Bu kimning nutqi?”, “Mening fikrimcha...”, “Chalkashtirish”.

Kalit so’zlar: Yozuvchi, adabiyot, innovatsiya, metodika, pedagogik texnologiya.

Abstract: This article contains innovative methodological recommendations used in teaching the stories of the Uzbek writer Abdullah Qahhor "The Sick" and "The Thief" to the younger generation. The following modern pedagogical technologies were used: "Explanation of terms", "Problem situation", "Five-part text", "Whose speech is this?", "In my opinion...", "Confusion".

Keywords: Writer, literature, innovation, methodology, pedagogical technology.

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Bugungi kunda yosh avlodni tarbiyalashda, ularga bilim berishda dunyo tan olgan ilmiy-innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish davr talabi. Shuni inobatga olib biz pedagog-o'qituvchilar oldimizda juda katta mas'uliyat turibdi. Ushbu natijaga erishishda o'zbek adabiyotshunoslarining ilmiy meroslarini o'quvchilarga innovatsion metodlar orqali yetkazish maqsadga muvofiq. Bu usul orqali o'quvchilarning dunyoqarashini kengaytirishga o'z hissamizni qo'shgan bo'lamiz. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti "Barchamizning kamol topishimizda o'zbek shoir va adiblarimizning – Olloh ularni rahmat qilsin– ulug' xizmatlari borligini doimo minnatdorlik bilan eslaymiz" – deb ta'kidlagan edi. Ana shu jihatdan Abdulla Qahhor ijodini o'rganish, tahlil qilish va yoshlarga yetkazish sharaflı vazifadir.

Ma'lumki , 6 va 7- sinf adabiyot darsliklarida Abdulla Qahhorning "Bemor" va "O'g'ri" hikoyalari berilgan. Adabiy ta'limda yosh psixologiyasiga ko'ra 6 va 7- sinflarga dars o'tish jarayonida o'qituvchilarga ko'proq o'yin metodlardan foydalanish tavsiya etiladi. Bu usul o'quvchilar e'tiborini darsga jalb qilishda yordam beradi, albatta. Mening fikrimcha, Abdulla Qahhor hikoyalarini o'rgatishda o'ylantiradigan, muammoli vaziyat hosil qiluvchi va shu bilan birga o'quvchini darsga qiziqtiradigan metodlardan foydalanish samaralidir.

Abdulla Qahhor hikoyalari qisqa va ixcham satrlarda ulkan mazmun ifoda etishi bilan ahamiyatlidir. Adibning hikoyalarida ko'tarilgan ijtimoiy muammolar va insoniy tuyg'ular uyg'unligi kitobxonni chuqurroq o'ylashga va fikrlashga undaydi. Ularni sodda tilda yangicha yondashuv asosida o'quvchiga yetkazib

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berish esa zamonaviy o'qituvchining asosiy vazifasidir.

Adabiy ta'limda "Bemor" hikoyasini o'quvchilarga o'rgatishda "Atamalar izohi", "Muammoli vaziyat", "KZIX" metodlaridan foydalanish yaxshi samara beradi.

"Atamalar izohi" metodi. Asardagi hozirgi kunda eskirib qolgan *izvosh, oq podsho, qabza, oftobshuvoq, chilyosin, Sim, gavron* kabi so'zlarni doskaga yozib, ularni izohlab beriladi.

Izvosh	ot qo'shilgan arava
Oq podsho	O'sha davrdagi Rossiyaning podshosi
Qabza	tutqich, dasta
Oftobshuvoq	bahorgi, ta'sir kuchi kam, yoqimli oftob
Chilyosin	Qur'onning "Yosin" surasini o'qish bilan bog'liq bo'lgan diniy odat, marosim
Sim	Farg'ona shahrining eski nomi
Gavron	tayoq, xivich

"Muammoli vaziyat" metodi.

Ushbu metod o'quvchilarni teran fikr yuritishga va muammolarni hal qilishga o'rgatadi.

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O'quvchilar bu topshiriqni quyidagicha bajarishadi:

1. Asar Sotiboldining bemor xotini haqida bo'lganligi uchun "Bemor" deb nomlangan.
2. Sotiboldining xotinini davolash uchun malakali shifokor kerak. Shifokorga olib borish uchun pul kerak. Sotiboldiga o'xshagan oddiy insonlarda o'z ehtiyojiga yetgulik pul bo'lishi uchun esa jamiyat taraqqiy etgan bo'lishi kerak. Jamiyatni taraqqiy qildirish uchun esa ilm-fan kerakdir!
3. Sotiboldi yashagan davr kishilarining barchasi bemor. Ya`ni ma`naviy bemor. Tabib ham, baxshi ham, Abdug'aniboy va Sotiboldi ham-butun jamiyat bemor. Shu sababli hikoya "Bemor" deb nomlangan.

"KZIX" (Kuchli jihatlar, zaif tomonlar, imkoniyatlar, xavf-xatar) metodi

"Bemor" hikoyasini o'rganishda, timsollarga – Sotiboldi timsoliga tavsif berishda "KZIX" metodidan foydalanilsa, yaxshi samara beradi. O'quvchilar to'rtta

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guruhga ajratiladi, har bir guruh tavsifga olinayotgan subyektning bir tomoni haqida ma'lumot beradi (boshqa guruhlarga qo'shimcha qilish imkonini berish mumkin). "Bemor" hikoyasidagi Sotiboldi timsoliga tavsif berish uchun qo'llangan "KZIX" metodi quyidagicha bajarilishi kutiladi:

K (kuchli jihatlari) – Sotiboldi bilagida kuchi bor, 25-35 yoshlar chamasidagi (agar uning bitta qiz farzandi borligi inobatga olinsa) kishi.

Z (zaif tomonlari) – kambag'al, qo'lida arzigulik kasbi yo'q. Nochorlikdan, kambag'allikdan chiqishning aniq yo'llarini bilmaydi: sodda, ishonuvchan.

I (imkoniyatlar) – xalqimizda izlagan imkoniyat topadi, o'limdan boshqasining chorasi bor kabi hikmatli so'zlar yuradi. Sotiboldi o'z xo'jayini Abdug'aniboyni insofga chaqirishi, undan moddiy yordam olishi yoki atrofidagi odamlardan ko'mak so'rashi mumkin edi-ku. Sotiboldining birorta ham do'sti yo'qmikan?!

X (xavf-xatar) – yosh qizchasining onasiz qolishi, oilada ayol – ona bo'lmasligi; bemorni tuzatish uchun olingan qarz oila kelajagini ham barbod qilishi, chunki qarz yangi qarzlarning tug'ilishiga sabab bo'lishi...

"O'g'ri" hikoyasini o'rganish "Besh bo'lakli matn", "Maqol yoki ibora" "Bu kimning nutqi?", "Mening fikrimcha..." metodlaridan foydalanilsa o'quvchi o'zi uchun yangiliklar kashf qiladi.

"Besh bo'lakli matn" usuliga tayangan holda guruhlarga "O'g'ri" hikoyasi matni besh qismga ajratib beriladi. O'quvchilar matn bilan tanishadilar va uning mazmunini bir-birlariga yetkazadilar. Bunday usul qisqa vaqt ichida hikoya matni

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bilan tanishish imkoniyatini beradi. O'qituvchi hikoya matnini guruhlarga taqsimlaydi va har guruhdan matnni ifodali o'qish, mazmunini so'zlab berish, matndagi eskirgan va tarixiy so'zlarning ma'nosini izohlash kabi vazifalarni topshiradi.

“Chalkashtirish” metodi. Bunda hikoyadagi barcha ibora va maqollar aralash holda yoziladi. O'quvchilar esa ularni bir biridan farqlaydilar va mazmunini izohlaydilar. Bunda o'qituvchi o'quvchilarni nafaqat adabiyot fanidan balki ona tilidan ham bilimni tekshirgan bo'ladi, ya'ni fanlararo integratsiyani amalga oshiradi.

Otning o'limi itning bayrami;

Dehqonning uyi kuysa kuysin, ho'kizi
yo'qolmasin; Qozonni suvga tashlab qo'yish
kerak bo'ladi; Tekinga mushuk oftobga
chiqmaydi;

Quruq qoshiq og'iz
yirtadi; Tapa sochi
tikka bo'ldi;

Fuqaroning arzga borishi arbobning izzati
bo'ladi; Begim deguncha kishining beli sinar
ekan; O'ynashmagil arbob bilan — seni urar
har bob bilan; Peshonam sho'r bo'lmasa.

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Maqol	Ibora
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“Bu kimning nutqi?” usuli yordamida har uchala guruhga alohida hikoya qahramonlarining (amin va pristav) nutqi yozilgan audiomatn eshittiriladi va ular bu nutq qaysi qahramonga tegishli ekanligini topadilar, guruh a'zolari shartga muvofiq berilgan nutqiy parchaning egasini topadilar.

Masalan, O'zi qaytib kelmasmikin!.. Birov olib ketsa qaytib kela ber, deb qo'yilmagan ekan-da! Nega yig'lanadi? A? Yig'lanmasin! (*Aminning nutqi*). O'quvchilarning nutq egasini topishi, “Bu -Aminning nutqidan” deyishi – yaxshi. Lekin o'quvchi shu bilan kifoyalaniq qolmasligi, berilgan nutqni tahlil qilishi, asar timsolining xarakterini belgilashda bu nutqning tutgan o'rnini aniqlashi, unga munosabat bildirib, bunday o'rinda qo'llanishi zarur bo'lgan nutqiy muloqotni misol keltira olishi – asosiy yutuq hisoblanadi.

“*Mening fikrimcha...*” metodi

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Mening fikrimcha o'g'ri bu...

Bu metod o'quvchilarni mustaqil fikrlashga o'rgatadi

Ushbu metoddan darsni xulosalash jarayonida foydalanish mumkin. Bunda o'quvchilar hikoya haqida o'zlarining shaxsiy fikrlarini bildiradilar. O'qituvchi esa bu fikrlarni umulashtirib darsni yakunlaydi.

Ushbu metodlar o'qituvchilarga innovatsion dars o'tish usuli sifatida tavsiya etiladi. Ulardan qay darajada foydalana olish esa har bir o'qituvchining metodik mahoratiga bog'liq.

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